

A HIGH AND INCREDIBLE REPRESENTATION OF THE EAST

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the life and activities of Yodgor Nasriddinova Sadiqovna, the first statesman to emerge in the 20th century, the only Uzbek woman who held one of the highest positions in a huge country like the USSR, and the first years of her political career.*

Keywords: *position, leader, management, communist party, Soviet system, Komsomol, political era, construction, engineer, secretary.*

Today, the world community recognizes the great attention paid to the issue of women in our country, especially the work being done to ensure gender equality in our society. As a result of these effective reforms, today women are effectively performing their activities in various fields of our country.

The life and activities of Yodgor Nasriddinova, who lived in the complicated political period of history (60s-70s of the 20th century) and worked effectively as a state and public figure, have not been fully studied in detail. Yodgor Nasriddinova is one of the first Uzbek women who worked in the most responsible positions not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the former USSR.

Yodgor Nasriddinova was born on December 26, 1920 in Kokan, Fergana region. Her father Sadiq Nasriddinov worked as a porter in the house of a rich man from Kokand and died of pneumonia before his daughter was born. After the death of her husband, the mother of Yodgor, Kumri Aya, was forced to go to her father's house, where she gave birth to her child. She names her child Yodgor as the only memory left by her husband. After that, he marries a second time by his father's order.

Yodgor Nasriddinova remembers this marriage of her mother and her youth in her interviews as follows: "My mother got married at the age of 13. I was born when he was widowed at the age of 15. At the age of 17, she was forced to marry a drug addict living in Yaipan village for the second time. But that man's family did not accept me. From that time, a two-year-old girl began to pass through the hands of childless people. I worked in their houses because I was afraid that these people would throw me out on the street. In 1931 (11 years old), when the first orphanage was opened in the village of Kudash near Kokan, I was saved from long wanderings in other people's homes and countless insults and bullying. Only here for the first time I had the opportunity to wear new clothes and study. At the age of 14, I entered the workers' school in Kokon and studied and worked to help my mother. That's how my childhood was"[1].

These childhood difficulties made Yodgor grow up as a more diligent, aspiring, strong-willed and determined person who overcomes all obstacles with patience.

At the age of 13, Yodgor was taken into the care of an elderly teacher, Kari-Charlie, and from that moment on, important changes began to take place in his life. When Kari-Charlie, childless, meets Yodgor on the street for the first time, she develops a special love for the little girl, and Yodgor's interest in education, high dreams, willpower to overcome difficulties and help her family as much as possible impresses the old teacher and decides to help her[2].

After that, Yodgor will be placed in the rabfak* with the help of Kari-Sharli. Having received a thorough education here, Yodgor entered the Central Asian Institute of Railway Transport Engineers, founded in 1931, and a year later, he won the "Stalin" scholarship. In 1941, he graduated and was awarded a Stalin scholarship due to his diligence until the end of his studies. Yodgor's interest in sports was also high, and in 1939, the leadership of Uzbekistan headed by U. Yusupov entrusted him to participate as a representative of the Uzbek SSR in the All-Union physical culture test, as he was an initiative, a member of the Komsomol, and the champion of the republic in running 1500 meters.

After the inspection, a reception will be organized in honor of the participants in the Grand Kremlin Palace, and the participants will be received by I. Stalin himself. After meeting with the bodybuilders, he stops in front of Yodgor Nasriddinova and asks, "Girl, where are you from?" he strokes his hair. And the young Uzbek girl answers: "I am from Uzbekistan, I play sports, work and study"[3].

After this event, Nasriddinova's political career made rapid progress, she became known in Uzbekistan, and words like "Equal to the monument" became the motto of every Uzbek girl.

His work started from his student days. Among the 200,000 people involved in the construction of the Great Fergana Canal, students also worked. Yodgor, who worked among them, quickly became known for his hard work and cheerfulness. Young Yodgor also worked as a "foreman" in the construction of the Kattakurgan reservoir. Yodgor Sodigovna, who has her own ideas and opinions during the work process, disagrees with the manager at the construction site of the Kattakurgan reservoir. In the mutual discussion, both parties considered their opinion to be correct and did not give in to each other. It was difficult for an experienced engineer to accept a young girl as an engineer and leader. After several hours of negotiations, the chief engineer, after listening to the opinions of others, admits that Yodgor is right[5].

A year later, Yodgor works as a regional leader in the construction of the Tashkent-Angren coal line. After graduating from the university, he joined the Tashkent railway station as a road maintenance engineer. Soon, great changes began to take place in his life. Yodgor's work book was filled with entries written in connection with the transfer to new positions every year.

It should be noted that Usman Yusupov played a big role in the rapid rise of Yodgor Nasriddinova's political career. Yo. Nasriddinova herself recalls this in an interview with Moskovsky Komsomolets: "On June 25, 1942, I was summoned to the Central Committee of the Republic before Usman Yusupov. Usman Yusupov told me: "Komsomol now needs an experienced Uzbek girl in organization." I objected, saying that I could not do these things. But the head of the republic did not accept my objection that "You grew up as an orphan, you are a foster child of an orphanage, you know life well"[6].

Thus, Yodgor was elected secretary of the Komsomol Central Committee for work with school youth and pioneers. It was at this time that Tashkent was filled with evacuees from the lands where the Second World War was ongoing. Yo. Nasriddinova was at the head of responsible work such as housing, feeding and providing clothes for 200,000 children from different regions of the USSR.

From February 1942 to January 1946, the Plenum of the Central Committee appointed Yodgor as the first secretary of the Komsomol Committee in the system of public education of the Republic. From January 1946 to March 1948, he was the first secretary of the Komsomol Committee of the Tashkent region, and from October 1948 to 1950, he was the second secretary

of the Komsomol Committee of Uzbekistan. From October 1950 to May 1952, he worked as the first secretary of the Kirov district of the Central Committee of Uzbekistan, and in 1952-1955, he was the head of construction of many construction objects in the republic. Yodgor Nasriddinova, during her work in this field, built powerful power plants, including Qayroq-Kum, Angren power station, construction of new factories, construction of carbide plant in Chirchik, construction of Samarkand superphosphate plant in 1955, laying of new roads, airlines, gas pipelines throughout the Republic, luxurious Pakhtakor stadium will lead the construction of the Tashkent TV Center. In September 1954, Yo.Nasriddinova was summoned to the Central Committee of the Republic and informed that she would go to China as part of the party's government delegation to celebrate the 5th anniversary of the founding of the People's Republic of China. During his trip to China, Yodgor met with the supreme political leader of the USSR N.S. Khrushchev[7]. It was this time that prompted Yodgor to open the doors of his political career.

Yo.Nasriddinova was distinguished from other leaders by her diligence and perfect execution of tasks on time, so in 1955-1959 she worked as a deputy of the Council of Ministers of the Republic, and in 1959-1970 as the chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan. During his career, he was awarded the Order of Lenin four times, the Order of the October Revolution, and the Order of the Red Banner of Labor twice.

At this point, let's briefly touch on the political system in the Uzbek SSR during the period of activity of Yodgor Nasriddinova. The 1950s of Uzbekistan's history was characterized by a number of conflicting situations, controversial situations in political and ideological processes, and some changes in the economic and social aspects.

In March 1953, I.Stalin's death and N.Khrushchev's seizure of power also affected the political processes in the Union republics. These changes in the management of power led to the strengthening of the influence of the communist party and its control over the state and executive bodies of the Uzbek SSR[8].

During the period when Yodgor Nasriddinova lived and worked, a unique system of political management (administrative-command) and a political elite was formed in the Uzbek SSR, like all allied republics. The personality cult of Stalin was deeply rooted. In the Uzbek SSR, as in the Soviet Union, it was formed on the basis of nomenclature. When the leaders of the Soviet state selected candidates for leadership from among the representatives of the local population, they first of all paid attention to their social origin, class and party status, loyalty to the communist ideology, unconditional fulfillment of any given tasks, and other aspects. Regarding the selection of leading personnel, the following orders were constantly received from the Center: "Special attention should be paid to people who have organizational skills and are popular among the people. It is necessary to try to recruit such people, if they refuse, it will be necessary to block their path to higher positions"[8].

Such various orders and decisions have always kept the national cadres under control, preventing them from independent thinking and putting forward new ideas. Anyone who acted in the national interest was a victim of repression.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the 1950s and 1960s in the Uzbek SSR, the administrative-command system of the Center became stronger, and incorrect, ill-thought-out decisions were made in social and economic policy. This later caused serious ecological problems in Uzbekistan, creation of fabrications such as "cotton case", "Uzbek case". As in the whole

country, in the Uzbek SSR, extremely negative vices such as bribery, embezzlement, and extortion became commonplace, and these processes deepened the crisis of the USSR and the Soviet system. Studying and objectively assessing the active and active activities of the first political leaders of Uzbekistan, who worked under the strong pressure and control of the center, is one of the important tasks facing the science of history. The work of Yodgor Nasriddinova Sodigovna is a part of Soviet history, and the negative events in politics should be studied based on the essence of the era in which she lived and the Soviet system. Naturally, it is not easy to make an objective assessment of Yo.Nasriddinova's outstanding activity, because Yodgor, like other leaders, faithfully served the Soviet government. Among the women of the East, she was the first statesman to emerge in the 20th century.

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